

Research protocol

Prevalence and quantification of pleural effusions and incidence of thoracentesis in patients admitted to the ICU: An observational, repeated cross-sectional study

Research group

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Background

Previous research has shown that the incidence or prevalence of pleural effusions in patients admitted to the ICU varies between 8% to 62% [1], [2] for radiographically confirmed diagnosis, and 37% to 81% [3]–[5] for sonographically confirmed diagnosis, depending on definition of effusion, type of Intensive Care Unit (ICU) (medical, surgical or mixed) and the specific patient population. Pleural drainage will be performed on some of these patients, as percutaneous pleural drainage is the third most frequent procedure in the ICU [6], but due to scarce evidence the indication and timing for when to drain pleural fluid is not yet standardized.

Pleural effusion

A pleural effusion is an excessive fluid accumulation in the pleural cavity surrounding the lungs. Pleural fluid is produced by the parietal circulation and is continuously reabsorbed by the lymphatic system: a pleural effusion develops when the rate of pleural fluid production exceeds the rate of reabsorption [7]. A pleural effusion may be related to disorders of the lung or pleura, or to a systemic disorder. Possible symptoms include pleuritic chest pain, dyspnea, and dry, nonproductive cough. One systematic review found that malignancies, congestive heart failure, parapneumonic effusions and tuberculosis are among the most common causes for pleural effusion in ICU patients [8]. Pleural effusions cause a restrictive ventilatory effect and are associated with expansion of the chest wall, which reduces the efficiency of the inspiratory muscles. Furthermore, pleural effusion can be associated with hypoxemia [9].

Ultrasonography

Assessment of the lung and pleura by ultrasound is a logical continuation of focused cardiac ultrasound in clinical practice and may help in the differential diagnosis between cardiac and respiratory etiology in patients with respiratory or circulatory insufficiency.

Lung ultrasound is a non-invasive and timesaving examination that often saves lives. It also has the advantage of repetency without increased risk of irradiation.

In clinical settings ultrasound may detect small pleural effusions (> 20 ml) and may approach the sensitivity and specificity of computed tomography [10][11].

During the last decade, ultrasonography has been used to directly quantify the volume of a given pleural effusion. Several formulas have been developed and to this end, three formulas demonstrate robust support in the literature, and are commonly used in clinical practice: the Balik formula, with the

patient in supine position and mild torso elevation at 15° [12], the Eibenberger formula, also using the supine position of the patient [10], and the Goecke formula, where the patient is in prone position [10]. No consensus on a best measurement method, best patient positioning, or best formula exists [13]. We will use the modified Balik formula, with the patient in supine position and elevated torso at 15°, as it is deemed most suitable for the current study.

Thoracentesis

Thoracentesis, i.e. pleural effusion drainage, can be performed surgically or by ultrasound guidance. Ultrasound guided thoracentesis is a percutaneous procedure where pleural fluid is removed through a needle or other drainage devices and can be performed bedside as well as in an emergency room or operating room. Sedation is not usually required, and the procedure is performed with the use of local anesthetics.

Pleural effusion drainage leads to an overall improvement of 18% in the ratio between partial pressure of arterial oxygen (PaO₂) and fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO₂) [14], and drainage of pleural effusions > 500 ml improves oxygenation and end-expiratory lung volume in mechanically ventilated patients [15].

The most common complication to thoracentesis is pneumothorax. One study reported that pneumothorax occurred in 6% of all cases, while a controlled study found that the use of ultrasound significantly lowered the rate of pneumothorax to 4%, vs. 9.3% for unguided thoracentesis [11] [12]. Other potential complications include pain at the puncture site, bleeding, vasovagal reactions, shortness of breath, cough, and re-expansion pulmonary edema [17]. Furthermore the risk for pneumothorax increases when large amounts of fluid are drained [18].

Despite pleural effusions occurring relatively frequently in the ICU, there are no clear guidelines with indications for thoracentesis regarding the weighting of the patient's condition, the size of the effusion, the need for drainage, and the spontaneous development with or without thoracentesis. Different studies however, have suggested the size of the pleural effusion, pleural fluid pH and measurement of chest wall compliance [19] [20] as factors to aid the decision-making process regarding when to drain pleural fluid, but there is little consensus on the topic.

The aim of this observational study is to characterize pleural effusions in patients admitted to the ICU, to quantify the prevalence and spontaneous development of such, as well as of any thoracentesis conducted in relation to the patients' clinical condition.

Methods

Design

This is a prospective longitudinal observational quality control study utilizing repeated cross-sectional ultrasonographic measurements.

Bilateral bedside pleural ultrasonography will be performed daily on patients admitted to the four ICUs at Aalborg University Hospital (Cardiac ICU (TIA), Neuro- and trauma ICU (NOTIA), Multidisciplinary ICU (R) and Pediatric and Obstetric ICU (103)) during a consecutive 14-day period in September 2021. The collected data will be compared to data from the electronic patient journal in relation to underlying cause, respiratory condition, coagulation status and drainage of pleura effusion.

Population

All patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria in the 14-day period will be enrolled.

Inclusion criteria

- Admitted to one of the four ICUs at Aalborg University Hospital
- Age ≥ 18 years

Ultrasonic measurements are part of the usual care at all four ICUs with evaluations of pulmonary and cardiac status. In this project, daily ultrasonic measurements will be performed to evaluate both pleural cavities. For patients in intermittently prone position, the ultrasonographic examination will be sought conducted in the time-intervals where the patient is supine.

Ultrasonographic measurements

The ultrasonographic assessment of the pleura will be performed with the patients in the supine position with a 15° elevation of the torso.

Bilateral pleural views will be obtained according to the Consensus Document ESC/EACVI for Focus Cardiac Ultrasound and Lung Ultrasound [21] by positioning the transducer in the posterior axillary line, with the orientation marker of the transducer directed towards the axil. The transducer must not be angled or tilted, which may result in a scan plane that is oblique to the transverse plane and ergo in an overestimation of the volume of pleural effusion.

A transverse section perpendicular to the body axis will be obtained, with the intrapleural fluid visible as an anechoic or hypoechoic layer between the parietal and visceral pleura.

The measurement will be performed at the lung basis, along a perpendicular line between the pleura visceralis and pleura parietalis, at the largest separation-point, after freezing the image at end-expiration or end-inspiration. The maximal pleural separation will be measured in expirium in mechanically ventilated patients and in inspirium in patients with spontaneous respiration [12].

The diaphragm, liver and spleen should be clearly visualized.

A plethysmography to indicate inspirium and expirium movements of the thorax associated with the US image will be used.

Fig. 1. Illustration of ultrasonographic measurement of the maximal separation between pleura parietalis and pleura visceralis (Sep) in a patient with clinically relevant pleural effusion.

To quantify the volume of pleural effusion, the simplified Balik formula will be used:

$$\text{Vol}_{(\text{ml})} = \text{Sep}_{(\text{mm})} \times 20 \text{ [12]}$$

Where: Vol = Volume (in ml) of pleural effusion and Sep = maximal separation between pleura parietalis and pleura visceralis (mm).

A Sep of more than 45 mm has been considered clinical relevant in earlier studies [12] but criteria that define clinical significance of pleural effusion in ICU patients are lacking [22].

In newer studies [23], a pleural effusion is considered clinically relevant when Sep is equal or greater than 20 mm together with a potential adverse effect on patient progress.

The examiners are four medical students or PhD students, possibly having no experience in ultrasound, but who have undergone a course in ultrasound, including six hours of e-learning and six hours workshop in 'Introduction to basic ABC ultrasound for medical students', approved by the university, followed by a practical exam as conducted at the university.

Before initiating the study, a clinical teacher, cardiothoracic anesthesiologist, having many years of experience in point of care ultrasound will conduct a four-hour review and a new exam of the four medical students.

All the examinations will be recorded by the students and reviewed by the clinical teacher.

All ultrasonographic measurements will be conducted using Vivid S5 or S6, or GE ultrasound units with cardiac transducers (3ScRS).

The examinations performed in this study are observational and are therefore not a part of the daily clinical practice at the included ICU departments, meaning that the respective physicians will not be informed of the results. However, if large pleural effusions are discovered, the information will promptly be forwarded to one of the physicians supervising the study; they will in turn make sure that relevant information is passed on to the respective physicians and/or that the findings are already documented in the patient journal and are being handled by the respective physicians.

Outcome measures

Primary outcome

- Proportion of patients with clinically relevant pleural effusion defined as a maximal separation between pleura parietalis and visceralis (Sep) > 20 mm, in either of the pleural cavities at any day in the ICU.

Secondary outcomes

- Proportion of patients with clinically relevant pleural effusion where thoracentesis was performed at any time during ICU stay.
 - Volume of pleural effusion (calculated from Sep) in the last ultrasonography of the relevant pleural cavity prior to thoracentesis.
 - Difference between ultrasonographic assessed fluid volume and the volume drained within approximately 24 hours after thoracentesis, the cumulated fluid out-put will be registered at fixed time-points every 8 hours at 06:00, 14:00 and 22:00.
- Spontaneous development of pleural effusion over time during ICU admittance in all patients, defined as Δ -volume of pleural effusion (calculated from Sep) in consecutive days after the first measurement day until pleural drainage, ICU discharge, death, or end of the observational period.
 - In patients with clinically relevant pleural effusion: spontaneous development of the pleural effusion over time during ICU admittance, defined as Δ -volume of pleural effusion (calculated from Sep) in consecutive days after the first day with Sep >20 mm until pleural drainage, ICU discharge, death, or end of the observational period.
- Proportion of patients without clinically relevant pleural effusion upon first ultrasonographic measurement developing clinically relevant pleural effusion during ICU stay.
- Proportion of patients with any pleural effusion defined as Sep > 5 mm in either of the pleural cavities.
- Maximal volume of pleural effusion (calculated from Sep) for all patients in either of the pleural cavities at any day in the ICU. In the event of bilateral pleural effusions, the total volume of effusions will be calculated as well.
- Proportion of patients where the ultrasound examination could not be performed on any day in the ICU (due to e.g. technical reasons, surgical fields, unable to position the patient in the required supine position) and proportion of all cumulated patient-days where it could not be performed.
- Cumulated daily intravenous fluid volume received and daily fluid balance based on the total calculated fluid intake minus the total fluid output.

Data

Patient data

Data will be collected from patient journals.

- Diagnosis/underlying cause/reason for admittance (emergency or elective, surgical or medical)
- Surgery performed (if relevant)
- Administered medicines (specifically antibiotics, decongestive, diuretic therapy)
- Parameters regarding
 - Infection

- Respiratory status, incl. mechanical ventilation, ventilator settings and oxygen therapy
- Arterial blood gas analyses
- Daily sequential organ failure assessment (SOFA) score [24]
- Simplified Acute Physiology Score (SAPS) 3 [25] upon admittance to the ICU
- Cardiological status, incl. echocardiography or other hemodynamic monitoring
- Inotropy and vasopressor administration
- Coagulation status incl. anticoagulant therapy
- Kidney function incl. dialysis, diuresis, creatinine, carbamide
- Fluids
- Liver function incl. albumin
- Cell count and culture test results for pleural exudate/transudate
- Culture test results for blood/expectorate/tracheal secrete
- Indication for thoracentesis if this is performed, as well as amount of drained fluid, including details on any thoracenteses conducted during current hospital admission, prior to or after the ICU admission or the observational period
- Chest X-rays and CT-scans
- Clinical outcomes incl. complications related to thoracentesis (e.g. infection, hemothorax, persistent pleural air leakage)
- Mortality rates during stay at hospital/ICU

Statistics

All data will be presented descriptively. Proportions as numbers and percentages, continuous data as means with 95% confidence intervals or medians with interquartile ranges as appropriate.

Supplemental graphs of development of pleural effusions by day in the ICU will be conducted.

Ethics

This research project will be performed in agreement with the Helsinki declaration [26]. According to national Danish legislation, quality control studies do not require ethical approval. This was confirmed upon specific request to The Committee on Health Research Ethics in the North Denmark Region (journal number 2021-000438). Approval to obtain data from patient medical journals was obtained from the local head of department as required.

Risks, complications

Lung ultrasonography is a non-invasive examination, which is routinely performed in the ICU on a daily basis. The examination can be associated with slight discomfort due to pressure against the thorax but no relevant complications to the examination exist and it bears no additional risks for the patients.

Biological material

No biological material will be collected or stored during this research project.

Processing of personal data

Data will be collected and managed using REDCap[®] electronic data capture tools hosted at the North Denmark Region [27] [28]. Electronic ultrasonographic images will be stored in the encrypted hard drives of the North Denmark Region. The study will be registered as required by the Danish Data Protection Agency.

Compensation for test subjects

There will not be provided compensation to the patients.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest for any of the parties involved.

Publication of results

The results of this research project will be published regardless of the outcomes. Publication will be sought in a relevant peer reviewed journal.

The final protocol is uploaded to Zenodo.org, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5509146 prior to study initiation.

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